

Heterocyclic Systems. Part III.¹ Sulphurisation of 1-Aryl-3-oxocyclohexenes as a Convenient Route to Hydrobenzonaphthothiophene Derivatives

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1-Aryl-5,5-dimethyl-3-oxocyclohexenes easily available by the reaction of arylmagnesium bromide with 5,5-dimethyl-3-ethoxycyclohex-2-en-1-one (enol ether of dimedone) afford hydroaromatic ketones containing thiophene ring on being heated with sulphur. The method constitutes a simple and convenient route to hydrobenzonaphthothiophene derivatives which are known to possess interesting physiological properties.

CONDENSED thiophene ring compounds specially naphtho [1, 2-b] thiophenes² and their partially hydrogenated derivatives³ show interesting physiological properties including antitumour activity⁴. They are sulphur isosteres of substituted indoles and are therefore anticipated to possess similar activities as some indole alkaloids⁵. Methods for synthesis of polycyclic thieno-compounds containing aromatic and heteroaromatic rings are available in the literature⁶. But most of them involve a long series of reactions and are not often simple. Of the various methods, two relatively recent syntheses of benzo [b] naphtho [2, 1-d] thiophene (III) are worth mentioning. One consists of a Pschorr cyclisation⁷ of appropriately substituted aminonaphthyl aryl sulphides (as I) and the other is an elegant photocyclisation⁸ of suitable styryl compounds (as II) (Scheme I). The starting materials of these syntheses are, however, not easy to get by. We

low yield is apparently due to a competing side reaction, namely, the facile aromatisation of the cyclohexenones to 3-arylphenols which do not undergo sulphurisation under the experimental condition. It is proposed that

Scheme 2

one of the reactive sites, C-2 and C-4 of the cyclohexenone moiety initiates the reaction depending on whether sulphur alone or with iodine is used. In view of the extreme simplicity of the reaction and easy accessibility of the starting materials, we thought it to be of interest to extend this one-step synthesis to other condensed thiophene ring compounds specially to hydrobenzo [b] naphtho [d] thiophenes which may prove to be physiologically important. A preliminary account of these experiments is presented in this communication.

Scheme 1

have recently reported¹ a one-step synthesis of benzo [b] naphtho [2, 1-d] thiophene derivatives by sulphurisation of easily accessible 1-aryl-3-oxocyclohexenes (Scheme 2). The simplicity of the method largely compensates for the relatively low yield of the reaction which seldom exceeds 30% after purification of the products. The

In order to avoid the premature aromatisation of the cyclohexenone ring which is mainly responsible for lowering the yield of the thiophene derivatives, geminally substituted cyclohexenones such as 1-aryl-5, 5-dimethyl-3-oxocyclohexenes (V) were chosen as substrates for sulphurisation. These were conveniently prepared by the reaction of arylmagnesium bromides with 5, 5-dimethyl-3-ethoxycyclohex-2-en-1-one (IV) (Scheme 3) which in turn was obtained from 5, 5-dimethylcyclohexane-1, 3-dione (dimedone)⁹. Three such ketones (VI), (VII), and (VIII) were heated with powdered sulphur and the product worked up in the usual way¹ to give 2, 2-dimethyl-1, 2, 3, 4-tetrahydridibenzothiophen-4-one (IX), 8, 8-dimethyl-7, 8, 9, 10-tetrahydrobenzo [b] naphtho [2, 1-d] thiophen-10-one (X), and 8,8-dimethyl-7,8,9,10-

tetrahydrobenzo [b] naphtho [1, 2-d] thiophen-10-one (XI) respectively (Scheme 3). The structures of the

Scheme 3

compounds were confirmed by their NMR and mass spectra (see Experimental). The yields (12, 40, and 35% respectively) are considerably higher than those obtained for the simple cyclohexenones described before¹ and may be improved since the reaction conditions are still to be optimised. Heating the ketones with sulphur in presence of iodine resulted into intractable tar. Apparently, the steric effect of the adjacent geminal dimethyl group prevented the alternative ring-closure involving C-4 which went very well with the simple 1-aryl-3-oxocyclohexenes¹.

It may be noted in this connection that for the ketone (VIII), an alternative ring closure with the peri position of the naphthalene nucleus is possible leading to the formation of a thiopyran derivative. Literature,^{10,11} however, reports that such cyclisation is at best a minor reaction and in the present case, no evidence was obtained for the existence of any isomeric product in the reaction mixture. The NMR data are consistent with the structure (XI) (see Experimental). The present method thus provides a good entry to condensed thiophene ring compounds which are capable of further chemical transformations.

Experimental

All melting points are uncorrected. The homogeneity of all compounds was checked by TLC. Petroleum refers to the fraction, b.p. 60–80°. NMR spectra were measured for solutions in CDCl_3 with tetramethylsilane as internal standard. The UV spectra were taken on a Cary 17D spectrophotometer in ethanol. Solutions were dried over anhydrous Na_2SO_4 .

5,5-Dimethyl-3-ethoxycyclohex-2-en-1-one (IV)⁹, b.p. 140°/8 mm and 5,5-dimethyl-3-oxo-1-phenylcyclohexene (VI),¹² m.p. 50–51° were prepared following literature procedure.

5, 5-Dimethyl-1-(2-naphthyl) cyclohex-2-en-1-one (VII): A solution of 5, 5-dimethyl-3-ethoxycyclohex-2-en-1-one (4.2 g, 0.025 mol) in dry ether (15 ml) was added dropwise to a Grignard solution prepared from magnesium (1.5 g), 2-bromonaphthalene (10.3 g, 0.05 mol), and ether (30 ml). The mixture was stirred overnight and then decomposed with cold dilute H_2SO_4 . The ethereal layer was separated, washed well with water, and dried. The solid obtained after evaporation of the solvent was absorbed on neutral alumina (120 g)

and eluted with petroleum-benzene (95:5). The first few eluents gave 2, 2'-binaphthyl, m.p. 185° while the latter eluents afforded 5, 5-dimethyl-1-(2-naphthyl)cyclohex-2-en-1-one (VII) (3.2 g), m.p. 83°; yield, 51%. (Found: C, 86.3; H, 7.5. Calc. for $\text{C}_{18}\text{H}_{18}\text{O}$: C, 86.4; H, 7.2%); ν_{max} (KBr) 1650 cm^{-1} ; τ (60MHz) 2.02–2.60 (7H, m, ArH), 3.45 (1H, t, J 1 Hz, 2-H), 7.23 (3H, t, J 1 Hz, 4-H₂), 7.63 (3H, s, 6-H₂), and 8.82 (6H, s, CMe_2).

5, 5-Dimethyl-1-(1-naphthyl) cyclohex-2-en-1-one (VIII): This was prepared in a similar way by reaction of 5, 5-dimethyl-3-ethoxycyclohex-2-en-1-one with 1-naphthylmagnesium bromide and was obtained in comparable yield as an oil, b.p. 140–150°/0.5 mm (Found: C, 86.1; H, 7.6%). ν_{max} 1650 cm^{-1} which could not be solidified on chromatography.

2, 2-Dimethyl-1, 2, 3, 4-tetrahydrodibenzothiofophen-4-one (IX): 5, 5-Dimethyl-3-oxo-1-phenylcyclohexene (VI) (1.0 g, 5 mmol) was intimately mixed with powdered sulphur (0.32 g, 10 mmol) and heated in a metal bath at 250–270° for 2 h. The product was taken up in ether, the organic layer thoroughly washed with aqueous 10% NaOH and dried. On removal of the solvent, a black semi-solid mass was obtained which was absorbed on a column of silica-gel (15.0 g). 2,2-Dimethyl-1,2,3,4-tetrahydrodibenzothiofophen-4-one (IX) was obtained by elution with petroleum-ether (95:5) as colourless flakes (0.125 g), m.p. 109–110.5° (ether-petroleum); yield, 12% (Found: C, 73.2; H, 6.2; S, 13.9; M^+ , 230. Calc. for $\text{C}_{14}\text{H}_{14}\text{OS}$: C, 73.05; H, 6.1; S, 13.9%; M , 230); ν_{max} (KBr) 1670 cm^{-1} ; λ_{max} 240 (ϵ 11,500), 250 (11,350), 297 (16,240), and 330 nm (sh) (4660); τ (100 MHz) 2.04–2.62 (4H, m, ArH), 7.06 (2H, s, 1-H₂), 7.44 (2H, s, 3-H₂), and 8.80 (6H, s, CMe_2).

8,8-Dimethyl-7,8,9,10-tetrahydrobenzo [b] naphtho [2-1-d]thiophen-10-one (X): 5,5-Dimethyl-1-(2-naphthyl)-3-oxocyclohexene (VII) (0.5 g) was likewise heated with powdered sulphur (0.13 g) and worked up in the same way. The product was absorbed on a column of silica-gel (10.0 g). Elution with petroleum-ether (95 : 5) afforded 8, 8-dimethyl-7, 8, 9, 10-tetrahydrobenzo [b] naphtho [2, 1-d] thiophen-10-one (X) (0.210 g), m.p. 201°; yield, 40% (Found: C, 76.95; H, 5.6; S, 11.6; M^+ , 280. Calc. for $\text{C}_{18}\text{H}_{18}\text{OS}$: C, 77.1; H, 5.7; S, 11.4%; M , 280); ν_{max} (KBr) 1648 cm^{-1} ; λ_{max} 223 (ϵ 18,900), 270(sh) (25,180), 280 (35,000), 325 (17,500), and 370 nm (sh) (3,500); τ (60 MHz) 1.70–2.52 (6H, m, ArH), 7.06 (2H, s, 7-H₂), 7.40 (2H, s, 9-H₂), and 8.80 (6H, s, CMe_2).

8,8-Dimethyl-7,8,9,10-tetrahydrobenzo [b] naphtho [1, 2-d] thiophen-10-one (XI): 5, 5-Dimethyl-1-(1-naphthyl)-3-oxocyclohexene (VIII) (1.0 g) and sulphur (0.256 g) was similarly heated at 250–270° for 2 hr to afford a solid which was absorbed on silica-gel (15.0 g). Elution with petroleum-ether (95 : 5) furnished 8, 8-dimethyl-7, 8, 9,10-tetrahydrobenzo [b] naphtho [1, 2-d] thiophen-10-one (XI) (360 mg); yield, 35%. On Sublimation and crystallisation from petroleum-ether, it furnished colourless plates, m.p. 163–164° (Found: C, 77.00; H, 5.9; S, 11.2. Calc. for $\text{C}_{18}\text{H}_{18}\text{OS}$: C,

77.1; H, 5.7; S, 11.4%); ν_{max} (KBr) 1665 and 1595 cm^{-1} ; λ_{max} 233 (ϵ 33, 250), 250 (sh) (14, 350), 278(sh) (11,200), and 330 nm (15,680); τ (100 MHz) 1.53 (1H, 2 x d, J 8 & 1 Hz, 6-H), 2.40–2.60 (5H, m, ArH), 6.62 (2H, s, 7-H₂), 7.40 (2H, s, 9-H₂), and 8.78 (6H, s, CMe₂). One interesting feature of the NMR spectrum was the appearance of the allylic methylene protons (7-H₂) at relatively low field (τ 6.62) as compared to similar methylene protons in compounds (IX) and (X) which appeared at τ 7.06. This was presumably due to the deshielding effect of the adjacent naphthalene ring as expected in the structure (XI). The isomeric thiopyran structure would not show this downfield shift. The present formulation thus stands confirmed. The mass spectrum showed prominent peaks at m/e 281 ($M+1$, 22%), 280 (M^+ , 100), 224 (45), 196 (39), 195 (23), and 152 (13).

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